

HOT DEFORMATION AND RECRYSTALLIZATION BEHAVIOUR OF A SiC_p/6061 Al COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Hot torsion behaviour and microstructure of a SiC particle reinforced 6061 Al alloy (15 vol.%, 18 μm diameter) are investigated. The equivalent stress-strain curves of hot torsion tests (ranging from 200 to 600°C and 0.1, 1.0 and 4.0 s⁻¹) show that the flow stresses of SiC_p/6061 Al are increased compared with those of an Al-Mg-Si alloy; this is mainly from the contribution of the SiC particle reinforcement. TEM observation reveals that there are some highly misoriented grains (2-3 μm) around the SiC particles which implies that they stimulate DRX at elevated temperatures. Very fine 200 nm precipitates are observed in the 6061 Al matrix. The dynamic recrystallized grains are stabilized by the very fine precipitates. The relationship between the precipitates and grains was found to fit the Anderson equation.

Keywords: metal-matrix composites, hot torsion, dynamic recrystallization, precipitates

1. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The 15 vol.% SiC_p/6061 Al composite was supplied by the Alcan Aluminum Corporation through its Kingston Laboratories. The chemical composition is given in Table 1. Torsion samples were machined from extruded bars and tested to fracture at strain rates ($\dot{\epsilon}$) of 0.1, 1.0 and 4.0 s⁻¹ and at temperatures (T) of 200, 300, 400 and 500°C. Details of specimens, torsion machine and experimental techniques have been described previously [1]. The specimens were immediately quenched after testing to retain the worked microstructure. A JEOL 2000CX transmission electron microscope was used for microstructural analysis.

Table 1. Chemical Composition of SiC_p/6061 Al

Matrix Elements (wt. %)						Reinforcement (vol. %)
Mg	Si	Cu	Fe	Mn	Al	SiC particles
1.0	0.6	0.3	0.7	0.15	Bal.	15

1.1 TEM Specimen Preparation

The TEM specimens were cut from hot torsion tested samples and ground to 200 μm thick slices. To minimize introduction of mechanical deformation, 3 mm diameter TEM specimens were prepared using a core drill with 40 μm diameter diamond cutting medium. Dimpling and ion milling techniques were used to obtain thin areas for TEM investigation.

2. RESULTS

2.1 Mechanical Tests

The torsional equivalent stress versus strain curves for $\text{SiC}_p/6061 \text{ Al}$ composite show much lower hardening behaviour at 200°C than at room temperature. At high temperatures, the flow stress finally becomes reasonably steady, but exhibits a slight drop at large strains which is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The equivalent stress versus equivalent strain curves of hot torsion tested $\text{SiC}_p/6061 \text{ Al}$ composite material [1].

2.2 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

Optical observation shows the SiC particles have an average size of $18 \mu\text{m}$. The as-cast constituent particles (Mg_2Si type) can not be easily identified because they have a similar size to the SiC particles. The TEM investigation shows that there are mainly two distinct sizes of crystallites (200-600 nm and 2-3 μm). Large regions of non-cellular structure with some equiaxed subgrains having an average size of 200-600 nm and misorientation less than 5° were observed in the deformed matrix after specimen fracture as shown in Figure 2. Some of the 200-600 nm and 2-3 μm subgrains/grains with misorientation larger than 25° are found around the SiC particles in the matrix (Figures 3 and 4). The faceted precipitates with an average size of 200 nm are observed at various test temperatures within the subgrains/grains interiors and on the boundaries (Figure 5).

Figure 2. Material deformed at 300°C , 1.0 s^{-1} : (a) non-cellular structure and (b) equiaxed subgrains.

Figure 3. Material deformed at 500°C , 1.0 s^{-1} showing 200-600 nm crystallites with misorientation larger than 25° : (a) image of the subgrains/grains and (b) diffraction pattern of the subgrains/grains.

Figure 4. Material deformed at 500°C, 1.0 s⁻¹ showing 2-3 μm subgrain/grains with misorientation larger than 25°: (a) image of the grains and (b) diffraction patterns of the grains.

Figure 5. Material deformed at 400°C, 1.0 s⁻¹ revealing 200 nm precipitates: (a) within subgrain/grain interiors and (b) on the boundaries.

3. DISCUSSION

The equivalent flow stress versus equivalent flow strain curves at various test temperatures show that SiC_p/6061 Al composite has a normal work hardening behaviour similar to other Al alloys at low strain conditions. A higher flow stress of SiC_p/6061 Al composite compared with that of Al-Mg-Si alloy [2] at various temperatures mainly comes from the contribution of the SiC particle strengthening. The drop of the flow stress for SiC_p/6061 Al at high temperature is due to the diffusion rate becoming faster and enhancing DRV. Local dynamic recrystallization (DRX) may also contribute to the softening on the stress-strain curve. The relation of the average subgrain size

and the temperature is still under investigation. The average level of dynamic recovery (DRV) appears much reduced compared to the bulk matrix alloy [3,4].

TEM observation of the hot torsion specimens at various temperatures shows a large region of non-cellular structure and equiaxed subgrains with an average size of 200-600 nm. The misorientation between the subgrains is less than 5°. They are the DRV subgrains. The difference in microstructure between the non-cellular and equiaxed substructures perhaps comes from the non-uniform distribution of the dislocation density between the SiC particles. TEM investigation shows that the percentage of the non-cellular substructure and equiaxed subgrains is 60-70% of the entire matrix. Thus DRV is still considered as the dominant mechanism in SiC_p/6061 Al composite during the hot deformation at $\dot{\epsilon} = 1.0 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

The 2-3 μm crystallites with misorientations larger than 25° or with different diffraction patterns are believed to be DRX grains. The 200-600 nm crystallites with misorientations larger than 25° or with different diffraction patterns are considered likely to be nuclei of DRX. The DRX area occupied about 30-40% of the matrix. It should be mentioned that the SiC particle volume fraction is only 15% in the material studied which may be not high enough to stimulate large scale DRX. The stress versus strain curves show a slight drop at or above 400°C. The softening behaviour of SiC_p/6061 Al composite at high strain and high temperatures may be explained by the local DRX.

The 200 nm precipitates are observed in the matrix. They precipitated during the deformation or from the original particles which is under investigation. Their volume fraction is about 3% [6]. It was also estimated from there being one precipitate per subgrain/grain which was ascertained by TEM observation. They are found inside the grains or on grain boundaries and may stabilize the boundary movement during DRX. The relationship between the 2-3 μm grains and 200 nm precipitates fits the Anderson equation below [5]:

$$D = 9r/f^{0.31} \quad (1)$$

where,

- D : average grain size
- r : radius of the precipitates
- f : precipitate volume fraction

4. CONCLUSIONS

- The equivalent stress-strain curves of SiC_p/6061 Al composite obey the normal high temperature hardening behaviour of Al alloys. The higher flow stress of the composites compared to an Al-Mg-Si alloy is mainly due to the contribution of the dislocations and substructure induced by flow around the SiC particles. The softening of SiC_p/6061 Al at high temperature arises from the increase of the diffusion rate thus DRV and also from local DRX. The average size of the subgrains has not shown an obvious correlation with the flow stress.

- Two types of the crystallite microstructure have been found in SiC_p/6061 Al composite. One with average size of 200-600 nm and misorientations less than 5° is composed of DRV subgrains. The one with an average size of 2-3 μm and misorientations larger than 25° is recognized as DRX grains.

- The large region (about 60-70% of the entire matrix) of subgrains exhibiting a range of development shows DRV is the dominant mechanism in $\text{SiC}_p/6061$ Al composite at $\dot{\epsilon} = 1.0 \text{ s}^{-1}$.
- The 200 nm precipitates possibly hinder the DRX grain boundary movement.

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